

Catholics in the People's Republic of China (PRC)

By John Lindblom, Univeristy of Notre Dame

Entry tags: Christian Traditions, Religious Group, Catholic, Chinese Religion, Chinese Christian Traditions, Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region

This group includes all Catholics in the People's Republic of China (PRC) (i.e. mainland China, excluding Taiwan, Hong Kong and Macau) from its founding in 1949 to the present. It includes believers who participate in the registered (or "above ground") part of the church as well as the unregistered (or "underground") part of the church, and those in both urban and rural locations. In 1949, when the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) led by Chairman Mao Zedong defeated the Nationalist Party (KMT), and established the PRC, there were an estimated four million Catholics in China. Whereas the KMT government supported them and had established diplomatic relations with the Vatican, the CCP (even before 1949) had begun to persecute Catholics as agents of foreign imperialism. Broader CCP efforts to eradicate all religion in favor of Marxist atheism began in the 1950s. Fr. Beda Chang (Zhang Boda 张伯达), the first Catholic martyr under CCP rule, was martyred in 1951. After resisting CCP pressure, a large group of Catholics in Shanghai, including its first Chinese bishop, Ignatius Kung Pin-mei (Gong Pinmei 龔品梅), was arrested in 1955. In 1957 the government established the Chinese Catholic Patriotic Association (CCPA), a government body responsible for ensuring compliance with the demand that the Church in China must be "independent" and self-sustaining, with no official ties to the Vatican or the Pope. A percentage of clergy accepted these demands, and formed the state-approved official, or "above-ground" church, while the majority of Catholics, who rejected these demands as incompatible with the Catholic faith, became known as the unofficial, or "underground" Church. The CCPA began orchestrating the appointment of bishops without papal approval, which continued until 2018, when a controversial agreement between the Holy See and the PRC government was signed. Since 2018, the government has continued to pressure underground clergy to agree to a separation, or "independence" from the Holy See. During the Cultural Revolution (1966-76), all perceived political enemies of Mao were persecuted, and believers of all religions, including official and underground Christians were killed or suffered mental or physical mistreatment. After Mao's death, official churches reopened, but still under the CCPA's oversight. To the surprise of many, the number of Christians had grown during these silent years, and continued to expand from the 1980s to the present. Today China has an estimated 10-12 million Catholics, and many more Protestant Christians.

Date Range: 1949 CE - 2020 CE

Region: People's Republic of China

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, China

Borders of present-day China

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Lu Nan. On the Road: The Catholic Church in China (photographs) -

<https://moom.cat/en/item/lu-nan-trilogy>

- Source 1: Edmond Tang, Jean-Paul Wiest. *The Catholic Church in Modern China*. Wipf and Stock Publishers. isbn: 9781625640864.
- Source 2: Richard Madsen. *China's Catholics*. Univ of California Press. isbn: 9780520920736.
- Source 3: C. Chu. *The Catholic Church in China*. Springer. isbn: 9781137075659.

Notes: See full Bibliography below

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.nytimes.com/2018/02/14/world/asia/china-catholics-vatican.html>.
- Source 1 Description: Article: Ian Johnson, "10 Million Catholics in China Face Storm They Can't Control," *The New York Times*, February 14, 2018, sec. World.
- Source 2 URL: <http://www.asianews.it/news-en/The-decline-of-China%E2%80%99s-Catholic-population-and-its-impact-on-the-Church-38373.html>
- Source 2 Description: Article: Anthony Lam Sui-ky, "The decline of China's Catholic population and its impact on the Church," *AsiaNews*, August 23, 2016.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.prcleader.org/sinicization-of-chinese-religions>.
- Source 3 Description: Article: Richard Madsen, "The Sinicization of Chinese Religions under Xi Jinping," *China Leadership Monitor*, September 1, 2019.

Notes: These authors present in-depth analysis of issues facing Catholics in China.

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.asianews.it/theme-en/China-1.html>
- Source 1 Description: A Catholic news outlet based in Rome reporting on the Catholic Church, other religions, general politics and human rights throughout Asia.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.catholicnewsagency.com/news/congressional-hearing-highlights-case-of-catholic-bishop-missing-in-china-61860>.
- Source 2 Description: Matt Hadro, "Congressional Hearing Highlights Case of Missing Chinese Catholic Bishop," *Catholic News Agency*, July 30, 2020.
- Source 3 URL: <http://www.asianews.it/news-en/Cardinal%27-Zen%27s-open-letter-in-response-to-Cardinal-Re%27s-criticism-49453.html>.
- Source 3 Description: Zen, Joseph. "Cardinal' Zen's Open Letter in Response to Cardinal Re's Criticism." *AsiaNews*, March 3, 2020.

Notes: This is a sample of the many news sources and voices commenting on the present situation facing Catholics in the PRC.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

- Source 1 URL: <http://hsstudyc.org.hk/index.htm>
- Source 1 Description: Holy Spirit Study Centre in Hong Kong: dedicated to information and analysis about the Catholic Church in China. Primary publication is the journal *Tripod*

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.usfca.edu/ricci-institute>

– Source 2 Description: Ricci Institute for Chinese-Western Cultural History: A resource for the study of Chinese-Western cultural exchange with a core focus on the social and cultural history of Christianity in China.

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.uscatholicchina.org/>

– Source 3 Description: U.S.-China Catholic Association: Inspired by the Gospel, the mission of the US-China Catholic Association is to build bridges of friendship and dialogue between people of China and the United States by offering educational, service, and cultural programs in support of the Church and the larger society.

Notes: These three organizations are resources for understanding the history and current circumstances of Catholics in China.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-pope-china/vatican-says-china-intimidating-catholics-loyal-to-pope-idUSKCN1TTIMY>.

– Source 1 Description: Article: Philip Pullella, "Vatican Says China Intimidating Catholics Loyal to Pope," Reuters, June 28, 2019.

– Source 2 URL: <https://berkeleycenter.georgetown.edu/responses/the-catholic-church-in-china-one-year-after-the-sino-vatican-agreement>

– Source 2 Description: Article: Beatrice Leung, "The Catholic Church in China: One Year After the Sino-Vatican Agreement," Berkley Center for Religion, Peace & World Affairs, November 26, 2019.

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.scmp.com/news/china/diplomacy/article/3093851/vatican-china-agreement-catholics-keep-faith-historic-deal>.

– Source 3 Description: Article: Mimi Lau, "Chinese Catholics Keep Faith in Historic Vatican Deal despite Slow Progress," South China Morning Post, July 20, 2020.

Notes: These articles present news and commentaries on recent events and issues facing Catholics in China.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <http://www.ricci.usfca.edu/library.html>

– Source 1 Description: Ricci Institute for Chinese-Western Cultural History: Specializes in the history of Catholic missions in China, with a large collection of primary source materials. The Library is the heart of the Ricci Institute and the online catalog is its primary gateway. Both Western language sources and materials in Chinese, Japanese, and Korean are cataloged. The Library provides service to Ricci Institute scholars and the USF community.

– Source 1 URL: <https://newbloommag.net/2019/12/03/cardinal-zen-interview/>.

– Source 1 Description: Haggerty, Nicholas, "Interview: Cardinal Joseph Zen (陳日君)," New Bloom Magazine, December 3, 2019. Interview with Cardinal Zen, Archbishop Emeritus of Hong Kong, on the Sino-Vatican agreement, which the Cardinal has strongly opposed.

– Source 2 URL: https://www.chinasource.org/resource-library/topic-index/catholicism/?fwp_resource_types=articles

– Source 2 Description: China Source Quarterly issue on Catholic Church in China, featuring articles on

various topics

– Source 1 URL: https://digitalcommons.whitworth.edu/cmh_digital_archive/

– Source 1 Description: China Mission Digital Archive: The historical photograph and print collection represented here consists of images held in the Sino-Missionary image archive, presently housed at Whitworth University's Department of History.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.americamagazine.org/china-doc>

– Source 1 Description: Short video documentary on Catholic Church in China

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.magnumphotos.com/newsroom/religion/on-the-road-the-catholic-church-in-china/>

– Source 1 Description: Black and white artistic photographs of underground Catholics by acclaimed photographer Lu Nan, from his book, *On the Road*.

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bE4zhbnH7PY>

– Source 2 Description: Rome Reports: 2016 documentary on the situation between the Holy See and Chinese government two years before the Sino-Vatican agreement of 2018.

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Chinese Catholics read the Christian scriptures, Old and New Testaments, in Chinese translation. Historically this has presented a number of challenges, as translators have faced the difficulties of presenting unfamiliar doctrines and cultural content to Chinese readers. Some translators have opted to stay as close as possible to the original Hebrew and Greek texts in their translations, often resulting in a Bible that conveys the biblical text accurately, but strikes Chinese readers as somewhat foreign in style. The most prominent Catholic translation of this type is called the *Studium Biblicum Franciscanum*, or “Sigao” version of 1968, which is the official Catholic version used in China today. Other translators have looked for equivalent expressions in Chinese in an attempt to make the scriptures as familiar and attractive as possible to Chinese readers. One notable translation of this type was published by John C. H. Wu (Wu Jingxiong) in 1946 (Psalms) and 1949 (New Testament). Many Chinese Catholics still regard this as the most beautiful and authentically Chinese translation ever made. Wu, for example, recomposed the Psalms using Tang dynasty and other Chinese poetic forms, and infused his New Testament translation with Chinese vocabulary and idioms borrowed from the Confucian, Daoist, Buddhist, and other classics. See references below to find these versions online.

Reference: Jingxiong, Wu. *Sheng Yong Yi Yi (the Psalms), and Xin Jing Quan Ji (the Complete New Testament)* Translated by Wu Jingxiong. Jesus Taiwan (online), n.d.. <http://jesus.tw>.

Reference: ccreadbible.org. “The Bible (sigao Version, Traditional Characters)”, n.d..

<https://www.ccreadbible.org/Chinese%20Bible/sigao>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: The scriptures are a collection of books spanning over a millennium and from different cultures. The Hebrew Bible, or Old Testament for Christians, is the scripture of the Jewish people. The New Testament is the story of Jesus Christ and the early Christian Church, told through the four Gospels, the Acts of the Apostles, Epistles, and one apocalyptic book (Revelation). It was collected and canonized in its present form during the fourth century A.D./C.E. Both Old and New Testaments are believed by Catholics to be inspired by God through the human faculties of the authors. Other theories of the nature of inspiration have been held by non-Catholic communities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Revealed by a high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Bishops, priests, theologians, and scripture scholars all receive training in teaching scripture.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: See "List of cathedrals in China" in reference.

Reference: Wikipedia. "List of Cathedrals in China". Wikipedia, n.d..

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_cathedrals_in_China.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is really no such thing as an average settlement. In a rural Catholic village, the church may be the largest, most centrally located building. In large cities, major churches may have existed for centuries, and while once considered large, may now be dwarfed by high rise buildings.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: The largest Catholic churches in China will usually be found in major cities or rural pilgrimage sites, of which there are dozens, if not hundreds throughout the country. There are four or five large churches in Beijing, the largest of which is said to be the Cathedral of the Immaculate Conception, or South Cathedral (Nantang), which is located at a site given by the Wanli Emperor to Jesuit Missionary Matteo Ricci during the late Ming dynasty, around 1605.

Reference: Wikipedia. "Cathedral of the Immaculate Conception, Beijing". Wikipedia, n.d..

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cathedral_of_the_Immaculate_Conception,_Beijing.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

Notes: China has many large Catholic cathedrals and large and small churches spread throughout the country. Perhaps the largest is the Immaculate Conception Cathedral in Beijing (South Cathedral or Nantang). Many of China's large cities have their own cathedrals, each with its own unique history.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: One example of a large historic Catholic settlement is Xujiahui in Shanghai, the location of St. Ignatius Cathedral.

Reference: Wu, Paul. "St. Ignatius Cathedral in Shanghai". China Christian Daily, August 19, 2019. http://chinachristiandaily.com/news/church/2019-08-19/st-ignatius-cathedral-in-shanghai_8506.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Estimates of the number of Catholics in China vary, and no reliable official statistics are available. Many groups have tried to come up with a reliable estimate, but none is able to produce a number with a high degree of certainty. The Holy Spirit Study Centre of the Diocese of Hong Kong estimated 10 million Catholics in China in 2019, including registered (official) and unregistered (underground). This number is within the usual range of 9-12 million, and seems plausible. The State Council of the PRC estimates around 6 million Catholics in registered churches only. The Chinese authorities only count Catholics within registered Churches, and it seems that there is no official acknowledgement of unregistered Catholics.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Persons born to Catholic parents are usually baptized and become Catholics as infants.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Persons not baptized at birth are free to enter the Church through baptism as children, youth, or adults.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Persons officially become members of the Catholic Church at baptism, whether this takes place in infancy or later.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Temples:

– No

Notes: The Catholic Church has some of the world's greatest basilicas, cathedrals, churches, chapels, shrines, etc., but does not call them temples. China has many of these great structures. See "cathedrals and churches" below.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Cathedrals and churches

Notes: The Catholic Church in China has many kinds of religious architecture, from magnificent

cathedrals and churches to simple chapels in rural villages. A variety of architectural styles exist, but a strong preference historically has been French Gothic Revival design. Many Catholic churches were built during the late 19th century, when French missionaries were highly influential in many places.

Reference: Clark, Anthony E.. *China Gothic*. University of Washington Press, 2020.
https://books.google.com/books/about/China_Gothic.html?hl=&id=6Cd2xAEACAAJ.

Reference: Wikipedia. "List of Cathedrals in China". Wikipedia, n.d..
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_cathedrals_in_China.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As above, the field doesn't know for sure, but the number of Catholics is estimated to be less than 1% of the total population.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Catholics generally are encouraged to evangelize, or give witness to their faith in order to attract others to faith in Christ, but not proselytize in the sense of attempting to persuade or coerce others to become members. In China proselytizing by Christians is illegal, and given the history of the persecution of Catholics, the orientation of most Catholics historically has been toward preservation rather than expansion. With the increased emphasis on evangelization in the Church in the past several decades, however, Catholics, especially young persons, have increasingly become aware of the call to evangelize and begun to engage in it. This includes Catholics in China, despite the particular difficulties.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The Chinese government views Christians, Protestants and Catholics, with suspicion, and has taken increasing measures to control their activities in recent years, especially through the revised Regulations on Religious Affairs, effective in 2018, and the Measures on the Management of Religious Groups, effective 2020.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Reference: Arrington, Aminta. "Recasting the Image: Celso Costantini and the Role of Sacred Art and

Architecture in the Indigenization of the Chinese Catholic Church, 1922–1933". *Missiology: An International Review* 41, no. 4 (September 13, 2013).
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0091829613497158>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Only religious public space
- Some public spaces

Notes: Chinese Catholics wear medals and crosses, carry rosaries or other sacred items, place religious objects in homes, churches (inside and outside) and other significant places.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

Notes: Upon the death (or in very rare instances, the resignation) of a pope, a new pope is chosen by the electors in the college of Cardinals from among their members. As of July 2020 there were 221 Cardinals, among them 122 Cardinal electors. Sources: https://press.vatican.va/content/salastampa/en/documentation/cardinali---statistiche/elenco_per_eta.html; https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_living_cardinals

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

Notes: The pope is elected by electors in the College of Cardinals. Bishops, who head dioceses, which represent geographic areas around the world, are chosen or approved by

the pope from candidates submitted from the hierarchy in a given country. In some historical periods, including in China from 1949-present, governments have claimed for themselves a role in the selection of bishops, and the PRC government since 1957 has orchestrated the ordinations and installations of bishops without the pope's approval. From the 1990s until 2018, some bishops were ordained with joint approval and appointed to lead dioceses in the official church, while underground bishops remained unrecognized by the government and were subjected to pressure to join the official (registered) church and the Chinese Catholic Patriotic Association (CCPA), a government body that governs the affairs of the official church. Underground Catholics have rejected the CCPA as a body whose aim is to separate the Church in China from union with the pope. They see this as a move which violates Catholic doctrine, which holds unity with the pope, as the successor of St. Peter, whom Jesus Christ in the Gospels appointed to lead the church (Matthew 16:18; John 21:15-19), to be an essential matter of faith. For this reason, Pope Benedict XVI, in his 2007 letter to Catholics in China, referred to the CCPA (though not by name) as being "incompatible with Catholic doctrine." A controversial new agreement on the appointment of bishops between the Holy See (the Vatican) and the government of the People's Republic of China (PRC) was signed in 2018, and since then (as of July 2020) five bishops have been ordained and installed with joint approval. Supporters of the agreement lauded the fact that the PRC government for the first time recognized the pope as head of the church, with authority to approve or disapprove candidates for bishop, while critics of the agreement said that the government used the agreement to add pressure to underground bishops to join the official church, and sign a pledge of de facto separation, termed "independence," from the Holy See.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

— No

Notes: See notes above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

— Yes

Notes: The pope is selected in a closed meeting called a conclave in which the Cardinal electors gather in the Sistine Chapel at the Vatican for prayer for God's guidance in selecting the next pope, and successive votes are held until a successor is chosen. They do not hold that God directly reveals the name of the new pope, but that He is at work

through the election process, in cooperation with the human actors.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: The pope is regarded as having the gift of infallibility when teaching in a specific mode, called *ex cathedra* ("from the chair") on specific matters of faith. This quality has often been misunderstood as a belief that all of a particular pope's opinions or teachings are infallible, which is not what the Church believes. Bishops are obliged to uphold the teachings of the church, but they are not regarded as infallible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

Notes: Chinese rulers throughout history have rejected Christianity and belief in God as presented by Christians. In the PRC era they have rejected anti-communist statements by previous popes, but these matters are not believed by Catholics to be covered by the quality of infallibility.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Persons born to Catholic parents are usually baptized and become Catholics as infants.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Persons not baptized at birth are free to enter the Church through baptism as children, youth, or adults.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Persons officially become members of the Catholic Church at baptism, whether this takes place in infancy or later.

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↳ Assigned by some other factor:

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

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Notes: Catholics generally are encouraged to evangelize, or give witness to their faith in order to attract

others to faith in Christ, but not proselytize in the sense of attempting to persuade or coerce others to become members. In China proselytizing by Christians is illegal, and given the history of the persecution of Catholics, the orientation of most Catholics historically has been toward preservation rather than expansion. With the increased emphasis on evangelization in the Church in the past several decades, however, Catholics, especially young persons, have increasingly become aware of the call to evangelize and begun to engage in it. This includes Catholics in China, despite the particular difficulties.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The Chinese government views Christians, Protestants and Catholics, with suspicion, and has taken increasing measures to control their activities in recent years, especially through the revised Regulations on Religious Affairs, effective in 2018, and the Measures on the Management of Religious Groups, effective 2020.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Estimates of the number of Catholics in China vary, and no reliable official statistics are available. Many groups have tried to come up with a reliable estimate, but none is able to produce a number with a high degree of certainty. The Holy Spirit Study Centre of the Diocese of Hong Kong estimated 10 million Catholics in China in 2019, including registered (official) and unregistered (underground). This number is within the usual range of 9-12 million, and seems plausible. The State Council of the PRC estimates around 6 million Catholics in registered churches only. The Chinese authorities only count Catholics within registered Churches, and it seems that there is no official acknowledgement of unregistered Catholics.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As above, the field doesn't know for sure, but the number of Catholics is estimated to be less than 1% of the total population.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

Notes: Upon the death (or in very rare instances, the resignation) of a pope, a new pope is chosen by the electors in the college of Cardinals from among their members. As of July 2020 there were 221 Cardinals, among them 122 Cardinal electors. Sources:

https://press.vatican.va/content/salastampa/en/documentation/cardinali---statistiche/elenco_per_eta.html; https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_living_cardinals

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

Notes: The pope is elected by electors in the College of Cardinals. Bishops, who head dioceses, which represent geographic areas around the world, are chosen or approved by the pope from candidates submitted from the hierarchy in a given country. In some historical periods, including in China from 1949-present, governments have claimed for themselves a role in the selection of bishops, and the PRC government since 1957 has orchestrated the ordinations and installations of bishops without the pope's approval. From the 1990s until 2018, some bishops were ordained with joint approval and appointed to lead dioceses in the official church, while underground bishops remained unrecognized by the government and were subjected to pressure to join the official (registered) church and the Chinese Catholic Patriotic Association (CCPA), a government body that governs the affairs of the official church. Underground Catholics have rejected the CCPA as a body whose aim is to separate the Church in China from union with the pope. They see this as a move which violates Catholic doctrine, which holds unity with the pope, as the successor of St. Peter, whom Jesus Christ in the Gospels appointed to lead the church (Matthew 16:18; John 21:15-19), to be an essential matter of faith. For this reason, Pope Benedict XVI, in his 2007 letter to Catholics in China, referred to the CCPA (though not by name) as being "incompatible with Catholic doctrine." A controversial new agreement on the appointment of bishops between the Holy See (the Vatican) and the government of the People's Republic of China (PRC) was signed in 2018, and since then (as of July 2020) five bishops have been ordained and installed with joint approval. Supporters of the agreement lauded the fact that the PRC government for the first time recognized the pope as head of the church, with authority to approve or disapprove candidates for bishop, while critics of the agreement said that the government used the agreement to add pressure to

underground bishops to join the official church, and sign a pledge of de facto separation, termed "independence," from the Holy See.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

Notes: See notes above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: The pope is selected in a closed meeting called a conclave in which the Cardinal electors gather in the Sistine Chapel at the Vatican for prayer for God's guidance in selecting the next pope, and successive votes are held until a successor is chosen. They do not hold that God directly reveals the name of the new pope, but that He is at work through the election process, in cooperation with the human actors.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: The pope is regarded as having the gift of infallibility when teaching in a specific mode, called *ex cathedra* ("from the chair") on specific matters of faith. This quality has often been misunderstood as a belief that all of a particular pope's opinions or teachings are infallible, which is not what the Church believes. Bishops are obliged to uphold the teachings of the church, but they are not regarded as infallible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

Notes: Chinese rulers throughout history have rejected Christianity and belief in God as presented by Christians. In the PRC era they have rejected anti-communist statements by previous popes, but these matters are not believed by Catholics to be covered by the quality of infallibility.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Chinese Catholics read the Christian scriptures, Old and New Testaments, in Chinese translation. Historically this has presented a number of challenges, as translators have faced the difficulties of presenting unfamiliar doctrines and cultural content to Chinese readers. Some translators have opted to stay as close as possible to the original Hebrew and Greek texts in their translations, often resulting in a Bible that conveys the biblical text accurately, but strikes Chinese readers as somewhat foreign in style. The most prominent Catholic translation of this type is called the *Studium Biblicum Franciscanum*, or “Sigao” version of 1968, which is the official Catholic version used in China today. Other translators have looked for equivalent expressions in Chinese in an attempt to make the scriptures as familiar and attractive as possible to Chinese readers. One notable translation of this type was published by John C. H. Wu (Wu Jingxiong) in 1946 (Psalms) and 1949 (New Testament). Many Chinese Catholics still regard this as the most beautiful and authentically Chinese translation ever made. Wu, for example, recomposed the Psalms using Tang dynasty and other Chinese poetic forms, and infused his New Testament translation with Chinese vocabulary and idioms borrowed from the Confucian, Daoist, Buddhist, and other classics. See references below to find these versions online.

Reference: Jingxiong, Wu. *Sheng Yong Yi Yi (the Psalms), and Xin Jing Quan Ji (the Complete New Testament)* Translated by Wu Jingxiong. Jesus Taiwan (online), n.d.. <http://jesus.tw>.

Reference: [ccreadbible.org](http://www.ccreadbible.org). “The Bible (sigao Version, Tradional Characters)”, n.d.. <https://www.ccreadbible.org/Chinese%20Bible/sigao>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: The scriptures are a collection of books spanning over a millennium and from different cultures. The Hebrew Bible, or Old Testament for Christians, is the scripture of the Jewish people. The New Testament is the story of Jesus Christ and the early Christian Church, told through the four Gospels, the Acts of the Apostles, Epistles, and one apocalyptic book (Revelation). It was collected and canonized in its present form during the fourth century A.D./C.E. Both Old and New Testaments are believed by Catholics to be inspired by God through the human faculties of the authors. Other theories of the nature of inspiration have been held by non-Catholic communities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Bishops, priests, theologians, and scripture scholars all receive training in teaching scripture.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: See "List of cathedrals in China" in reference.

Reference: Wikipedia. "List of Cathedrals in China". Wikipedia, n.d..
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_cathedrals_in_China.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is really no such thing as an average settlement. In a rural Catholic village, the church may be the largest, most centrally located building. In large cities, major churches may have existed for centuries, and while once considered large, may now be dwarfed by high rise buildings.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: The largest Catholic churches in China will usually be found in major cities or rural pilgrimage sites, of which there are dozens, if not hundreds throughout the country. There are four or five large churches in Beijing, the largest of which is said to be the Cathedral of the Immaculate Conception, or South Cathedral (Nantang), which is located at a site given by the Wanli Emperor to Jesuit Missionary Matteo Ricci during the late Ming dynasty, around 1605.

Reference: Wikipedia. "Cathedral of the Immaculate Conception, Beijing". Wikipedia, n.d..
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cathedral_of_the_Immaculate_Conception,_Beijing.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

Notes: China has many large Catholic cathedrals and large and small churches spread throughout the country. Perhaps the largest is the Immaculate Conception Cathedral in Beijing (South Cathedral or Nantang). Many of China's large cities have their own cathedrals, each with its own unique history.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: One example of a large historic Catholic settlement is Xujiahui in Shanghai, the location of St. Ignatius Cathedral.

Reference: Wu, Paul. "St. Ignatius Cathedral in Shanghai". China Christian Daily, August 19, 2019. http://chinachristiandaily.com/news/church/2019-08-19/st-ignatius-cathedral-in-shanghai_8506.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Temples:

– No

Notes: The Catholic Church has some of the world's greatest basilicas, cathedrals, churches, chapels, shrines, etc., but does not call them temples. China has many of these great structures. See "cathedrals and churches" below.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Cathedrals and churches

Notes: The Catholic Church in China has many kinds of religious architecture, from magnificent cathedrals and churches to simple chapels in rural villages. A variety of architectural styles exist, but a strong preference historically has been French Gothic Revival design. Many Catholic churches were built during the late 19th century, when French missionaries were highly influential in many places.

Reference: Clark, Anthony E.. *China Gothic*. University of Washington Press, 2020.
https://books.google.com/books/about/China_Gothic.html?hl=&id=6Cd2xAEACAAJ.

Reference: Wikipedia. "List of Cathedrals in China". Wikipedia, n.d..
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_cathedrals_in_China.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Reference: Arrington, Aminta. "Recasting the Image: Celso Costantini and the Role of Sacred Art and Architecture in the Indigenization of the Chinese Catholic Church, 1922-1933". *Missiology: An*

International Review 41, no. 4 (September 13, 2013).
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0091829613497158>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Only religious public space
- Some public spaces

Notes: Chinese Catholics wear medals and crosses, carry rosaries or other sacred items, place religious objects in homes, churches (inside and outside) and other significant places.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans’ behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: In this and many of the following questions about beliefs, it is important to note that differences may be observed among Catholics in rural versus urban areas. Historically, the majority of China’s Catholics have lived in rural villages, and many grouped themselves together forming villages that were largely or entirely Catholic. Shifts in society in recent decades have changed these dynamics to some degree, but there are still many rural Catholic villages. Scholars such as sociologist Richard Madsen and

historian Henrietta Harrison have published their observations based on fieldwork in rural Catholic villages, some of which are cited in this section. In some cases, they find similarities between attitudes and behaviors among Catholics and those found in the pervasive local folk culture. Some of these will be discussed below. For reference, see, for example, Richard Madsen, *China's Catholics*, Chapter 3, "Morality and Spirituality," and Henrietta Harrison, *The Missionary's Curse*, Chapter 5, "The Missionary who Cursed the Village." There are also numerous other sources which have done historical or other kinds of fieldwork among Chinese Catholics in various locations.

Reference: Madsen, Richard. *China's Catholics*. University of California Press, 1998.
https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=U_8oMo2hnGMC.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

— Yes

Notes: Catholic Christianity, like other Christian traditions and Judaism, upholds the Ten Commandments found in the Old Testament (Exodus 20) as the basic moral standard for believers, and teaches followers to strive for an even higher goal, that of fulfilling Christ's commandments to love God with all one's heart, soul, mind, and strength, and one's neighbor as oneself (Matthew 22: 37-40), and even one's enemies (Matthew 5:44). Richard Madsen observed, however, that moral standards for rural Catholics in China, while upholding the Ten Commandments and Christ's teaching, also reflected the pervasive folk culture. For example, he writes, that in the view of Chinese Catholic villagers, "A good person is someone who has been good for a Catholic community. In practice, loyalty seems to be the cardinal virtue. People of poor character are those who are consistently disloyal, who consistently use others for their own selfish ends." Further, noting the importance Catholic villagers place on the traditional Confucian virtue of filial piety, Madsen continues, "For all the talk about the Ten Commandments...rural Catholic moral imagination is dominated by the Fourth Commandment--honor thy father and mother--and by the virtue of family loyalty, which makes adherence to that commandment reliable and consistent. Loyalty toward parents is both the core of good character and the core of a right relation to God. As a thirty-year-old Catholic mother says, 'Belief in God is just like having filial piety toward parents. A person cannot forget his parents, should speak with them often, should not be indifferent to them'" (Madsen, *China's Catholics*, 79). This emphasis on loyalty, Madsen found, manifests itself in certain results, which can be seen positively or negatively. Those admired most among Catholics are those who have demonstrated the strongest loyalty to Christ during persecution under the Communist Party (1949-present), and have suffered abuse (physical and especially mental abuse is reported to have been especially severe during the Cultural Revolution) or even literal martyrdom. Given the central place of loyalty, says Madsen, "those who are uncompromisingly loyal to fellow Catholics who have loyally suffered martyrdom can claim a preeminent moral superiority." (83) This emphasis on uncompromising loyalty, on the other hand, can also lead to a "rigid intransigence" and factionalism that prevents one from compromise, even when that might be called for by Christ's commands to avoid judging others and to love one's enemies (83). At the same time, Madsen writes that although those who failed to show a high degree of loyalty and self-sacrifice under persecution, as for example during the Cultural Revolution (1966-1976), are not held up as moral exemplars, they are nevertheless not judged harshly by fellow Catholics (82). Ultimately, Madsen explains, one's conduct is a matter of

salvation or damnation (86). See explanations in questions about rewards and punishments below.

Reference: Madsen, Richard. *China's Catholics*. University of California Press, 1998.
https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=U_8oMo2hnGMC.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

— Yes

Notes: The Catholic Church does not use the word taboo or believe that God punishes arbitrarily. In both the Old and New Testaments, God is described (and describes Himself) primarily as a loving and merciful Father who is quick to forgive His children. At the same time, He wants human beings to love Him and each other, do good and avoid evil, and has made the difference known clearly through Divine Revelation, which includes explicit commands, namely the Ten Commandments, through the revelation of Himself in the person of Jesus Christ, who is God incarnated as a man (John 1:1-14) and through conscience, or innate knowledge of right and wrong, justice and injustice, which is given to every human being. If "taboo" here is taken to mean the following, "the avoidance of a specific behavior for fear of harm by a dangerous power, or of dangerous pollution caused by the intermixing of incompatible powers. Taboo circumscribes some kind of supernatural threat that is usually simply termed "danger" (<https://anthropology.iresearchnet.com/taboo/>), then perhaps an anthropologist might attribute the term to God's punishments, but in Catholic (and other Christian) belief they would be seen as the ultimate results of wicked behavior, illustrated by the teaching of St. Paul that "whatever a man sows, that shall he also reap" (Galatians 6:7). Punishments are usually not imposed as a direct one-to-one repayment for specific deeds (although there are some examples of this in the Old and New Testaments), but either as the cumulative bad harvest from one's own bad choices (akin to the saying, "live by the sword, die by the sword," or one's reckoning with God at the final judgement. In China, however, taboos do exist in folk culture, and in one example of actual possible "taboos" from a Catholic village, Henrietta Harrison writes of well-known folktales of villagers regarding European missionaries, primarily from the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, as "outsiders with dangerous powers who must not be offended." In one such tale, a French missionary priest cursed a village, whose Christian believers tried to prevent him from taking a beautiful statue of Our Lady of Lourdes (a famous Catholic shrine in France) with him when he moved away to another parish. According to the tale, "He called the villagers Judeans, and as he left he took off his shoe, shook off the dust, and prayed to Heaven to punish them with seven years of bad harvests," a calamity which then came to pass. Afterwards, remembering his words, the villagers built a chapel to Our Lady of the Seven Sorrows, which still exists today (Harrison, *Missionary's Curse*, 116-17). Harrison notes that similar folktales used to be told about skilled foremen who directed work in the coal mines, who could destroy a whole mine if they were offended. The shrine to Our Lady of the Seven Sorrows is believed to demonstrate the "great power" of Our Lady (the Virgin Mary) and to be responsible for various miracles (117). Harrison writes that this story varies according to whether those telling it are local Catholic or non-Catholic villagers, and in her view, "Underlying all versions of the story is tension between the power of the missionaries and the poverty and dependence of the villagers" (117). The fact that this and similar stories are told differently according to whether the teller is Catholic or non-Catholic, and the similarity with other Chinese folktales, suggests that the actual historical event upon which it is based probably did not occur as the tale later recalled. It would be highly unusual for a missionary Catholic priest to have attempted to curse a village with seven years of bad harvests, the Church itself would condemn such an action by the priest, and does not believe that priests have the power to cause such misfortunes. The story, with mixed elements of Christian biblical actions, such as the shaking of dust off one's feet, which is an instruction given by Jesus to His disciples in the gospels if a town refuses to receive them, and Chinese folk religious suspicions, i.e.

the cursing of the villagers who angered the foreign priest, serves as a fascinating example of how Catholic villagers made sense of local historical events.

Reference: Harrison, Henrietta. *The Missionary's Curse and Other Tales from a Chinese Catholic Village*. University of California Press, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=Bk7jQaCuIEsC>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Food:

— Yes

Notes: The Catholic Church teaches that the Holy Eucharist is truly the Body and Blood of Jesus Christ, which he instituted at the Last Supper (Matthew 26: 26-27). It is regarded as the preeminent Sacrament of the Church. Many Catholics have associated various miracles throughout history with the Eucharist. According to the Catechism, "The Eucharist is 'the source and summit of the Christian life.' 'The other sacraments, and indeed all ecclesiastical ministries and works of the apostolate, are bound up with the Eucharist and are oriented toward it. For in the blessed Eucharist is contained the whole spiritual good of the Church, namely Christ himself, our Pasch.'" (Catechism of the Catholic Church, 1324) As such, Catholics treat the Host, or consecrated bread in which Christ is believed to be Really Present, with the utmost reverence. In Catholic teaching it is only to be consumed by Catholics who are in a state of grace. It is reserved in a sacred vessel called a tabernacle in a prominent place inside a Catholic Church, is displayed in a cross-shaped vessel called a monstrance before which people are invited to pray and adore Christ, and on special occasions it is taken in solemn procession outside the church, sometimes through the streets of the city or village. Catholics are taught to genuflect (bend one knee to the ground) and make the sign of the cross with their right hand when passing by the Eucharist or entering a church. Catholics in China, as in many countries throughout the world treat the Eucharist with this sense of reverence. In addition, Catholics worldwide customarily follow dietary disciplines during the penitential season of Lent, 40 days preceding Easter. This includes two fast days and abstaining from meat on Fridays. In practice, this is not highly burdensome. In China and some other countries, Catholics often abstain from meat on Fridays throughout the year, not only in Lent.

Reference: Catholic Church. *Catechism of the Catholic Church*. USCCB Publishing, 2000. https://books.google.com/books/about/Catechism_of_the_Catholic_Church.html?hl=&id=rEGcXz8GT3sC.

Sacred space(s):

— Yes

Notes: Catholics, including in China, hold Catholic Churches and special pilgrimage sites to be Sacred spaces where one is to show reverence and respect for the space itself and for fellow pilgrims or believers there. They are places of prayer and often fervent devotion. Shrines dedicated to the Virgin Mary are especially beloved by Chinese Catholics. Richard Madsen observed, "The central pictures in most rural churches and most true-believing homes are of the Blessed Virgin." Mary is seen as gentle, warm, and compassionate, able to comfort believers during times of terrible suffering, such as the Cultural Revolution, and when no priests were available to offer the sacraments. Madsen notes further, "The

eager acceptance of the Marian cult by Chinese Catholics was the result at least partly of Mary's resemblance to the Buddhist Guanyin and to the Eternal Mother of north Chinese secret societies" (88).

↳ Sacred object(s):

— Yes

Notes: The Catholic Church believes that all of creation is sacred, and uses a rich array of sacred objects, include Church buildings, liturgical (ritual) objects including statues, altars, tabernacles, baptismal fonts, icons, vessels of the altar consecrated for sacred use (chalice, paten, ciborium, monstrance, etc.), the priest's vestments (stole, chasuble, etc.), sacred art and music, and others. Special outdoor shrines depicting saints or the life of Christ, the Stations of the Cross, the Sorrows of Mary, etc., and personal religious objects including rosaries, missals, medals, and others, all of which can be blessed by a priest with holy water or with the sign of the cross made with his hand. In addition to these, the Church has a long and rich tradition of venerating the relics of saints, which fall into different classes, the highest (first class) being a piece of a saint's body such as bone, skin, or hair, or the saint's clothing or item the saint owned, touched, or something (such as a cloth) that has touched one of these. Beyond these, the Church blesses believers themselves at every mass and on any occasion for which it is requested, and almost any object considered to be important for religious use or in the lives of the faithful, including homes, vehicles, pets or livestock, land, etc.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

— Yes [specify]: Catholics believe that God care about all human affairs and concerns.

Reference: Giussani, Luigi. *The Religious Sense*. McGill-Queen's Press - MQUP, 1997.
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Religious_Sense.html?hl=&id=WYF3Y_zT8zoC.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

— Yes

Notes: Murder is forbidden in the Ten Commandments.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

— Yes

Notes: Christianity teaches that sexual intercourse or other sexual behaviors are only proper between a man and woman in marriage. This is evident throughout the Bible, starting with the earliest chapters of the first book, Genesis. The Catholic Church teaches that intercourse and most kinds of foreplay are permitted within marriage, as long as they respect the dignity of both persons, and culminate with ejaculation in the vagina. These norms may not always be well-known among Chinese Catholics, however, so different views may be held among them (continued in "Other sexual practices" below). For more information see Gregory K. Popcak, *Holy Sex*: https://www.goodreads.com/book/show/2091923.Holy_Sex_ and Christopher West, *Good News about Sex and Marriage*: https://www.goodreads.com/book/show/401803.Good_News_About_Sex_Marriage

Reference: Sheen, Fulton J.. *Three to Get Married*. Scepter Publishers, 2017. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=u-iUDgAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Paul, John. *Love and Responsibility*. Ignatius Press, 1993. https://books.google.com/books/about/Love_and_Responsibility.html?hl=&id=TNRY9HKssDQC.

Reference: West, Christopher. *Good News About Sex & Marriage* (revised Edition). Franciscan Media, 2018. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=H4tSDwAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Popcak, Gregory K.. *Holy Sex!*. Crossroad, 2008. https://books.google.com/books/about/Holy_Sex.html?hl=&id=FUPTIAAACAAJ.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Adultery:

— Yes

Notes: Adultery, including fornication, is forbidden by the Ten Commandments.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Incest:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other sexual practices:

— Yes [specify]: See notes

Notes: The Catholic Church is known as one of the only religious bodies to forbid the use of artificial means of contraception as a violation of the dignity of persons by artificially

suppressing a person's natural quality of fertility. In practice, many Chinese Catholic couples, possibly 1) because they have not learned the Church's teaching on contraception in depth and how to use natural means to avoid conception, which are approved by the Church, but primarily 2) because the totalitarian government has forcefully implemented birth limits under the one-child policy (in place from 1979 until 2015) and two-child policy (2015-present), most Chinese Catholic couples also have only one or two children (possibly more in remote areas), and have resorted to the use of contraception, which is mandated and monitored by the state, under the threat of punishment by the state for those who refuse. The state has also used widespread forced abortion to keep population numbers down throughout society, including Catholics.

Reference: Mosher, Steven W.. *A Mother's Ordeal*. Sphere, 1995.
https://books.google.com/books/about/A_Mother_s_Ordeal.html?hl=&id=B0A_HQAACAAJ.

Reference: Fong, Mei. *One Child*. Houghton Mifflin Harcourt, 2015.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=CLTqDwAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Johnson, Kay Ann. *China's Hidden Children*. University of Chicago Press, 2016.
https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=_w2ZCwAAQBAJ.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

— Yes

Notes: Bearing false witness is forbidden in the Ten Commandments.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

— Yes

Notes: Sorcery is forbidden for Christians in the New Testament.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

— Yes

Notes: "Honor your father and mother" is one of the Ten Commandments, and is given strong emphasis by Chinese Catholics, in keeping with the strong Chinese tradition of filial piety, or xiao, treating one's parents and ancestors with respect. In Chinese culture traditionally, respect is also due to elders in society in general. Chinese children frequently refer to almost any elder of the family's acquaintance as "auntie" or "uncle."

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

— Yes

Notes: Gossiping is explicitly condemned in the New Testament.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

— Yes

Notes: Stealing is forbidden in the Ten Commandments.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

— Yes

Notes: Catholics are obliged to participate in Mass (the Mass itself is a prayer) at least every Sunday if possible. Other devotions such as praying the rosary, adoration of the Holy Eucharist, and pilgrimages, are also popular. At the same time, it is a major theme throughout the Old and New Testaments that God does not care about the external performance of ritual acts or sacrifices, but about the inner disposition, or purity, of one's heart. Jesus said the two greatest

commandments are to love God and love one's neighbor, and stressed that the genuineness of one's love is of the greatest importance, and condemned those who made a show of their own ritual practices.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

— No

Notes: See note on previous question. While it is true that God the Father in the Old Testament and Jesus Christ in the New Testament condemn the performance of rituals if they are nothing more than a hypocritical display of supposed piety, China traditionally placed a strong emphasis on ritual, and Chinese Catholics do in fact usually observe a high degree reverence and piety when praying at Mass or other group or private prayer. One who observes Chinese Catholics at these prayers will often be struck by the degree of fervent participation, singing, chanting, etc., which contrasts with the often more subdued atmosphere in Catholic churches in the west.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

— Yes

Notes: Christians are explicitly commanded by Jesus Christ in the gospels to "go and make disciples of all nations" and baptize them in the name of the Father, Son, and Holy Spirit. Chinese Catholics in the PRC period have not gone out to evangelize in this way with as much zeal as Protestant Christians, largely because Catholics have been in a defensive state from a hostile government and Communist party. Since 1949, numbers of Christians both Protestant and Catholic have grown enormously, but Protestant Christianity has grown much more rapidly, and has many more adherents today. This was not the case in the years before 1949.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

— Yes

Notes: Stealing is forbidden in the Ten Commandments. Usury, withholding wages, and other forms of economic cheating are also condemned in the Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

— Yes

Notes: It is not quite accurate to say that in Christianity God does not care about personal hygiene--after all, the ritual by which one becomes a Christian, baptism, is a ritual cleansing of the body. Jesus Christ teaches and shows in the gospels, however, that what is important is to be clean in one's heart more than one's body. He demonstrated this by healing and embracing lepers, considered the most unclean in society, and by telling parables, such as Lazarus and the rich man, in which a poor beggar ends up in heaven, while a rich man who ignored him ends up in fiery torment.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Supernatural beings care about other:

—Yes [specify]: Christianity (including Catholics and Protestants) emphasizes that the faithful, both individually and corporately, enjoy an intimate, familial relationship, or covenant, with the Holy Trinity: Father, Son, and Holy Spirit. Thus, the Old and New Testaments emphasize that the condition of one's heart in relation to God is of the greatest importance, and ritual observances are meaningless unless they support this living relationship.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

— Yes

Notes: Notes: Catholic Christianity, like other Christian traditions and Judaism, upholds the Ten Commandments found in the Old Testament (Exodus 20) as the basic moral standard for believers, and teaches followers to strive for an even higher goal, that of fulfilling Christ's commandments to love God with all one's heart, soul, mind, and strength, and one's neighbor as oneself (Matthew 22: 37-40), and even one's enemies (Matthew 5:44). Richard Madsen observed, however, that moral standards for rural Catholics in China, while upholding the Ten Commandments and Christ's teaching, also reflected the pervasive folk culture. For example, he writes, that in the view of Chinese Catholic villagers, "A good person is someone who has been good for a Catholic community. In practice, loyalty seems to be the cardinal virtue. People of poor character are those who are consistently disloyal, who consistently use others for their own selfish ends." Further, noting the importance Catholic villagers place on the traditional Confucian virtue of filial piety, Madsen continues, "For all the talk about the Ten Commandments...rural Catholic moral imagination is dominated by the Fourth Commandment--honor thy father and mother--and by the virtue of family loyalty, which makes adherence to that commandment reliable and consistent. Loyalty toward parents is both the core of good character and the core of a right relation to God. As a thirty-year-old Catholic mother says, 'Belief in God is just like having filial piety toward parents. A person cannot forget his parents, should speak with them often, should not be indifferent to them'" (Madsen, *China's Catholics*, 79). This emphasis on loyalty, Madsen found, manifests itself in certain results, which can be seen positively or negatively. Those admired most among Catholics are those who have demonstrated the strongest loyalty to Christ during persecution under the Communist Party (1949-present), and have suffered abuse (physical and especially mental abuse is reported to have been especially severe during the Cultural Revolution) or even literal martyrdom. Given the central place of loyalty, says Madsen, "those who are uncompromisingly loyal to fellow Catholics who have loyally suffered martyrdom can claim a preeminent moral superiority." (83) This emphasis on uncompromising loyalty, on the other hand, can also lead to a "rigid intransigence" and factionalism that prevents one from compromise, even when that might be called for by Christ's commands to avoid judging others and to love one's enemies (83). At the same time, Madsen writes that although those who failed to show a high degree of loyalty and self-sacrifice under persecution, as for example during the Cultural Revolution (1966-1976), are not held up as moral exemplars, they are nevertheless not judged harshly by fellow Catholics (82). Ultimately, Madsen explains, one's conduct is a matter of salvation or damnation (86). See explanations in questions about rewards and punishments.

Reference: Madsen, Richard. *China's Catholics*. University of California Press, 1998.

https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=U_8oMo2hnGMC.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Alive, identified:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Coming has already passed:

– Yes

Notes: Christians believe that the Messiah of Israel and of all humanity is Jesus Christ, who lived in present-day Israel/Palestine around 4 B.C./B.C.E to around 30 A.D./C.E.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Chinese Catholics believe in the traditional doctrines of Heaven for believers who die in God's grace, and Hell for those who reject God. Richard Madsen found that Chinese Catholics also made creative use of the theological theory of limbo, held to be a state apart from Heaven or Hell where unbaptized infants went, but which the Vatican in 2007 declared to be incorrect. Madsen found that Chinese Catholics "filled the empty doctrine of limbo with a rich Chinese folk-religious content," believing it to be the final destination of their non-Catholic acquaintances (87).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: As explained above, the moral norms revealed by God clearly belong in the moral category, but may overlap with the conventional. As Richard Madsen found, the emphasis on loyalty among Chinese Catholic villagers may constitute an example of a conventional norm being given moral significance by believers. In Madsen's view, the virtue of loyalty in China is sometimes taken to an extreme, and becomes a kind of inflexibility, inability to compromise, or factionalism which becomes harmful to unity or reconciliation in the larger community.

Reference: Madsen, Richard. *China's Catholics*. University of California Press, 1998.

https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=U_8oMo2hnGMC.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Weakly present

Notes: Generally the distinction is present and clear, as in the case of the Ten Commandments, which are displayed in churches, but as Madsen shows, the conventional social values can sometimes be imposed by members of the community on each other as if they were moral values.

Reference: Madsen, Richard. *China's Catholics*. University of California Press, 1998.
https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=U_8oMo2hnGMC.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: See notes on "general social norms" above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

Notes: Moral norms are explicitly linked to God's design for human flourishing. Every positive command leads to human happiness, even if humans find them difficult to keep. Every negative command prohibits something that leads to human unhappiness, and in the church's view this is evident as it plays out in human history.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: This is true if one regards God as an anthropomorphic being. If not, then no.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: This is true if one regards God as an anthropomorphic being. If not, then no. In Christianity, God has made His commands clear, as explained above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

Notes: Moral norms have consequences, both in this life and potentially in eternity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Moral norms apply to:

- All individuals within society
- All individuals within contemporary world
- All individuals (any time period)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– I don't know

Notes: Generally Christianity believes that punishment is reserved to God alone: "Vengeance is mine, says the Lord." There is at least one passage in the Psalms which says that punishment of God's enemies will be carried out by His followers, but this is likely not taught as a point of Catholic doctrine, and may be more of a literary device.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done randomly:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other [specify]
– Yes
Notes: Punishment in the afterlife in Christianity is seen only as the result of a person's own choices to willfully separate himself or herself from God, who is the source of all life and goodness. In the absence of all goodness, such a person would experience separation and suffering, but it would not be arbitrary or random.
Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– I don't know
Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Yes

Notes: Traditionally, Catholic thought has characterized Hell as a place or state of eternal fire and torment.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Notes: In Christianity, eternal life is described as perfect, eternal union with God (Father, Son, and Holy Spirit) and all other inhabitants of Heaven: saints, angels, cherubim, etc., who worship God and enjoy pure fellowship with each other. In the Catholic Church, this state is traditionally called the "Beatific vision." (From Wiki) In Christian theology, the beatific vision (Latin: visio beatifica) is the ultimate direct self-communication of God to the individual person. A person possessing the beatific vision reaches, as a member of redeemed humanity in the communion of saints, perfect salvation in its entirety, i.e. heaven.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: There are passages in the Bible, such as the Psalms, which say that those who follow the Lord will be blessed, sometimes with abundance, blessings upon descendants, good health, long life, peace in one's heart, and other things. There are other stories, especially in the Old Testament, of individuals being granted specific requests for a child, victory in battle, and other blessings. The Catholic Church, including in China, teaches that believers may ask God for these things, and as the Psalm says, "give success to the work of our hands." Catholics do not believe, however, that God promises always to grant these requests. Often they are not fulfilled, and Christ, in fact, promised that his followers would undergo sufferings, but that these would lead to greater virtues and eternal life. The greatest gifts, according to the Bible, are spiritual: wisdom, good judgement, love, and other virtues.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: Traditionally, the Catholic Church encouraged burial of the bodies of the dead, although cremation has been declared acceptable, as long as the remains are treated as sacred and buried or interred in a permanent place such as a cemetery.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Mummification:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ As cenotaphs:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other formal burial type:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Chinese Catholics believe in the traditional doctrines of Heaven for believers who die in God's grace, and Hell for those who reject God. Richard Madsen found that Chinese Catholics also made creative use of the theological theory of limbo, held to be a state apart from Heaven or Hell where unbaptized infants went, but which the Vatican in 2007 declared to be incorrect. Madsen found that Chinese Catholics "filled the empty doctrine of limbo with a rich Chinese folk-religious content," believing it to be the final destination of their non-Catholic acquaintances (87).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: Traditionally, the Catholic Church encouraged burial of the bodies of the dead, although cremation has been declared acceptable, as long as the remains are treated as sacred and buried or interred in a permanent place such as a cemetery.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Mummification:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Feeding to animals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Secondary burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ As cenotaphs:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other formal burial type:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Supernatural Beings

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: In this and many of the following questions about beliefs, it is important to note that differences may be observed among Catholics in rural versus urban areas. Historically, the majority of China's Catholics have lived in rural villages, and many grouped themselves together forming villages that were largely or entirely Catholic. Shifts in society in recent decades have changed these dynamics to some

degree, but there are still many rural Catholic villages. Scholars such as sociologist Richard Madsen and historian Henrietta Harrison have published their observations based on fieldwork in rural Catholic villages, some of which are cited in this section. In some cases, they find similarities between attitudes and behaviors among Catholics and those found in the pervasive local folk culture. Some of these will be discussed below. For reference, see, for example, Richard Madsen, *China's Catholics*, Chapter 3, "Morality and Spirituality," and Henrietta Harrison, *The Missionary's Curse*, Chapter 5, "The Missionary who Cursed the Village." There are also numerous other sources which have done historical or other kinds of fieldwork among Chinese Catholics in various locations.

Reference: Madsen, Richard. *China's Catholics*. University of California Press, 1998.
https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=U_8oMo2hnGMC.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Catholic Christianity, like other Christian traditions and Judaism, upholds the Ten Commandments found in the Old Testament (Exodus 20) as the basic moral standard for believers, and teaches followers to strive for an even higher goal, that of fulfilling Christ's commandments to love God with all one's heart, soul, mind, and strength, and one's neighbor as oneself (Matthew 22: 37-40), and even one's enemies (Matthew 5:44). Richard Madsen observed, however, that moral standards for rural Catholics in China, while upholding the Ten Commandments and Christ's teaching, also reflected the pervasive folk culture. For example, he writes, that in the view of Chinese Catholic villagers, "A good person is someone who has been good for a Catholic community. In practice, loyalty seems to be the cardinal virtue. People of poor character are those who are consistently disloyal, who consistently use others for their own selfish ends." Further, noting the importance Catholic villagers place on the traditional Confucian virtue of filial piety, Madsen continues, "For all the talk about the Ten Commandments...rural Catholic moral imagination is dominated by the Fourth Commandment--honor thy father and mother--and by the virtue of family loyalty, which makes adherence to that commandment reliable and consistent. Loyalty toward parents is both the core of good character and the core of a right relation to God. As a thirty-year-old Catholic mother says, 'Belief in God is just like having filial piety toward parents. A person cannot forget his parents, should speak with them often, should not be indifferent to them'" (Madsen, *China's Catholics*, 79). This emphasis on loyalty, Madsen found, manifests itself in certain results, which can be seen positively or negatively. Those admired most among Catholics are those who have demonstrated the strongest loyalty to Christ during persecution under the Communist Party (1949-present), and have suffered abuse (physical and especially mental abuse is reported to have been especially severe during the Cultural Revolution) or even literal martyrdom. Given the central place of loyalty, says Madsen, "those who are uncompromisingly loyal to fellow Catholics who have loyally suffered martyrdom can claim a preeminent moral superiority." (83) This emphasis on uncompromising loyalty, on the other hand, can also lead to a "rigid intransigence" and factionalism that prevents one from compromise, even when that might be called for by Christ's commands to avoid judging others and to love one's enemies (83). At the same time, Madsen writes that although those who failed to show a high degree of loyalty and self-sacrifice under persecution, as for example during the Cultural Revolution (1966-1976), are

not held up as moral exemplars, they are nevertheless not judged harshly by fellow Catholics (82). Ultimately, Madsen explains, one's conduct is a matter of salvation or damnation (86). See explanations in questions about rewards and punishments below.

Reference: Madsen, Richard. *China's Catholics*. University of California Press, 1998.
https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=U_8oMo2hnGMC.

Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: The Catholic Church does not use the word taboo or believe that God punishes arbitrarily. In both the Old and New Testaments, God is described (and describes Himself) primarily as a loving and merciful Father who is quick to forgive His children. At the same time, He wants human beings to love Him and each other, do good and avoid evil, and has made the difference known clearly through Divine Revelation, which includes explicit commands, namely the Ten Commandments, through the revelation of Himself in the person of Jesus Christ, who is God incarnated as a man (John 1:1-14) and through conscience, or innate knowledge of right and wrong, justice and injustice, which is given to every human being. If "taboo" here is taken to mean the following, "the avoidance of a specific behavior for fear of harm by a dangerous power, or of dangerous pollution caused by the intermixing of incompatible powers. Taboo circumscribes some kind of supernatural threat that is usually simply termed "danger" (<https://anthropology.iresearchnet.com/taboo/>), then perhaps an anthropologist might attribute the term to God's punishments, but in Catholic (and other Christian) belief they would be seen as the ultimate results of wicked behavior, illustrated by the teaching of St. Paul that "whatever a man sows, that shall he also reap" (Galatians 6:7). Punishments are usually not imposed as a direct one-to-one repayment for specific deeds (although there are some examples of this in the Old and New Testaments), but either as the cumulative bad harvest from one's own bad choices (akin to the saying, "live by the sword, die by the sword," or one's reckoning with God at the final judgement. In China, however, taboos do exist in folk culture, and in one example of actual possible "taboos" from a Catholic village, Henrietta Harrison writes of well-known folktales of villagers regarding European missionaries, primarily from the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, as "outsiders with dangerous powers who must not be offended." In one such tale, a French missionary priest cursed a village, whose Christian believers tried to prevent him from taking a beautiful statue of Our Lady of Lourdes (a famous Catholic shrine in France) with him when he moved away to another parish. According to the tale, "He called the villagers Judeans, and as he left he took off his shoe, shook off the dust, and prayed to Heaven to punish them with seven years of bad harvests," a calamity which then came to pass. Afterwards, remembering his words, the villagers built a chapel to Our Lady of the Seven Sorrows, which still exists today (Harrison, *Missionary's Curse*, 116-17). Harrison notes that similar folktales used to be told about skilled foremen who directed work in the coal mines, who could destroy a whole mine if they were offended. The shrine to Our Lady of the Seven Sorrows is believed to demonstrate the "great power" of Our Lady (the Virgin Mary) and to be responsible for various miracles (117). Harrison's writes that this story varies according to whether those telling it are local Catholic or non-Catholic villagers, and in her view, "Underlying all versions of the story is tension between the power of the missionaries and the poverty and dependence of the villagers" (117). The fact that this and similar stories are told differently according to whether the teller is Catholic or non-Catholic, and the similarity with other Chinese folktales, suggests that the actual historical event upon which it is based probably did not occur as the tale later recalled. It would be highly unusual for a missionary Catholic priest to have attempted to curse a village with seven years of bad harvests, the Church itself would condemn such an action by the priest, and does not believe that priests have the power to cause such misfortunes. The story, with mixed

elements of Christian biblical actions, such as the shaking of dust off one's feet, which is an instruction given by Jesus to His disciples in the gospels if a town refuses to receive them, and Chinese folk religious suspicions, i.e. the cursing of the villagers who angered the foreign priest, serves as a fascinating example of how Catholic villagers made sense of local historical events.

Reference: Harrison, Henrietta. *The Missionary's Curse and Other Tales from a Chinese Catholic Village*. University of California Press, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=Bk7jQaCu1EsC>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Food:

– Yes

Notes: The Catholic Church teaches that the Holy Eucharist is truly the Body and Blood of Jesus Christ, which he instituted at the Last Supper (Matthew 26: 26-27). It is regarded as the preeminent Sacrament of the Church. Many Catholics have associated various miracles throughout history with the Eucharist. According to the Catechism, "The Eucharist is 'the source and summit of the Christian life.' 'The other sacraments, and indeed all ecclesiastical ministries and works of the apostolate, are bound up with the Eucharist and are oriented toward it. For in the blessed Eucharist is contained the whole spiritual good of the Church, namely Christ himself, our Pasch.'" (Catechism of the Catholic Church, 1324) As such, Catholics treat the Host, or consecrated bread in which Christ is believed to be Really Present, with the utmost reverence. In Catholic teaching it is only to be consumed by Catholics who are in a state of grace. It is reserved in a sacred vessel called a tabernacle in a prominent place inside a Catholic Church, is displayed in a cross-shaped vessel called a monstrance before which people are invited to pray and adore Christ, and on special occasions it is taken in solemn procession outside the church, sometimes through the streets of the city or village. Catholics are taught to genuflect (bend one knee to the ground) and make the sign of the cross with their right hand when passing by the Eucharist or entering a church. Catholics in China, as in many countries throughout the world treat the Eucharist with this sense of reverence. In addition, Catholics worldwide customarily follow dietary disciplines during the penitential season of Lent, 40 days preceding Easter. This includes two fast days and abstaining from meat on Fridays. In practice, this is not highly burdensome. In China and some other countries, Catholics often abstain from meat on Fridays throughout the year, not only in Lent.

Reference: Catholic Church. *Catechism of the Catholic Church*. USCCB Publishing, 2000. https://books.google.com/books/about/Catechism_of_the_Catholic_Church.html?hl=&id=rEGcXz8CT3sC.

Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: Catholics, including in China, hold Catholic Churches and special pilgrimage sites to be Sacred spaces where one is to show reverence and respect for the space itself and for fellow pilgrims or believers there. They are places of prayer and often fervent devotion. Shrines dedicated to the Virgin Mary are especially beloved by Chinese Catholics. Richard Madsen observed, "The central pictures in most rural

churches and most true-believing homes are of the Blessed Virgin." Mary is seen as gentle, warm, and compassionate, able to comfort believers during times of terrible suffering, such as the Cultural Revolution, and when no priests were available to offer the sacraments. Madsen notes further, "The eager acceptance of the Marian cult by Chinese Catholics was the result at least partly of Mary's resemblance to the Buddhist Guanyin and to the Eternal Mother of north Chinese secret societies" (88).

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: The Catholic Church believes that all of creation is sacred, and uses a rich array of sacred objects, include Church buildings, liturgical (ritual) objects including statues, altars, tabernacles, baptismal fonts, icons, vessels of the altar consecrated for sacred use (chalice, paten, ciborium, monstrance, etc.), the priest's vestments (stole, chasuble, etc.), sacred art and music, and others. Special outdoor shrines depicting saints or the life of Christ, the Stations of the Cross, the Sorrows of Mary, etc., and personal religious objects including rosaries, missals, medals, and others, all of which can be blessed by a priest with holy water or with the sign of the cross made with his hand. In addition to these, the Church has a long and rich tradition of venerating the relics of saints, which fall into different classes, the highest (first class) being a piece of a saint's body such as bone, skin, or hair, or the saint's clothing or item the saint owned, touched, or something (such as a cloth) that has touched one of these. Beyond these, the Church blesses believers themselves at every mass and on any occasion for which it is requested, and almost any object considered to be important for religious use or in the lives of the faithful, including homes, vehicles, pets or livestock, land, etc.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Catholics believe that God care about all human affairs and concerns.

Reference: Giussani, Luigi. *The Religious Sense*. McGill-Queen's Press - MQUP, 1997.
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Religious_Sense.html?hl=&id=WYF3Y_zT8zoC.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is forbidden in the Ten Commandments.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: Christianity teaches that sexual intercourse or other sexual behaviors are only proper between a man and woman in marriage. This is evident throughout the Bible, starting with the earliest chapters of the first book, Genesis. The Catholic Church teaches that intercourse and most kinds of foreplay are permitted within marriage, as long as they respect the dignity of both persons, and culminate with ejaculation in the vagina. These norms may not always be well-known among Chinese Catholics, however, so different views may be held among them (continued in "Other sexual practices" below). For more information see Gregory K. Popcak, *Holy Sex*: https://www.goodreads.com/book/show/2091923.Holy_Sex_and and Christopher West, *Good News about Sex and Marriage*: https://www.goodreads.com/book/show/401803.Good_News_About_Sex_Marriage

Reference: Sheen, Fulton J.. *Three to Get Married*. Scepter Publishers, 2017.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=u-iUDgAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Paul, John. *Love and Responsibility*. Ignatius Press, 1993.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Love_and_Responsibility.html?hl=&id=TNRY9HkssDQC.

Reference: West, Christopher. *Good News About Sex & Marriage* (revised Edition). Franciscan Media, 2018. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=H4tSDwAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Popcak, Gregory K.. *Holy Sex!*. Crossroad, 2008.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Holy_Sex.html?hl=&id=FUPTIAAACAAJ.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Adultery, including fornication, is forbidden by the Ten Commandments.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: See notes

Notes: The Catholic Church is known as one of the only religious bodies to forbid the use of artificial means of contraception as a violation of the dignity of persons by artificially suppressing a person's natural quality of fertility. In practice, many Chinese Catholic couples, possibly 1) because they have not learned the Church's teaching on contraception in depth and how to use natural means to avoid conception, which are approved by the Church, but primarily 2) because the totalitarian government has forcefully implemented birth limits under the one-child policy (in place from 1979 until 2015) and two-child policy (2015-present), most Chinese Catholic couples also have only one or two children (possibly more in remote areas), and have resorted to the use of contraception, which is mandated and monitored by the state, under the threat of punishment by the state for those who refuse. The state has also used widespread forced abortion to keep population numbers down throughout society, including Catholics.

Reference: Mosher, Steven W.. *A Mother's Ordeal*. Sphere, 1995.
https://books.google.com/books/about/A_Mother_s_Ordeal.html?hl=&id=B0A_HQAACAAJ.

Reference: Fong, Mei. *One Child*. Houghton Mifflin Harcourt, 2015.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=CLTqDwAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Johnson, Kay Ann. *China's Hidden Children*. University of Chicago Press, 2016. https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=_w2ZCwAAQBAJ.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Bearing false witness is forbidden in the Ten Commandments.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Sorcery is forbidden for Christians in the New Testament.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: "Honor your father and mother" is one of the Ten Commandments, and is given strong emphasis by Chinese Catholics, in keeping with the strong Chinese tradition of filial piety, or xiao, treating one's parents and ancestors with respect. In Chinese culture traditionally, respect is also due to elders in society in general. Chinese children frequently refer to almost any elder of the family's acquaintance as "auntie" or "uncle."

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: Gossiping is explicitly condemned in the New Testament.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: Stealing is forbidden in the Ten Commandments.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Catholics are obliged to participate in Mass (the Mass itself is a prayer) at least every

Sunday if possible. Other devotions such as praying the rosary, adoration of the Holy Eucharist, and pilgrimages, are also popular. At the same time, it is a major theme throughout the Old and New Testaments that God does not care about the external performance of ritual acts or sacrifices, but about the inner disposition, or purity, of one's heart. Jesus said the two greatest commandments are to love God and love one's neighbor, and stressed that the genuineness of one's love is of the greatest importance, and condemned those who made a show of their own ritual practices.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– No

Notes: See note on previous question. While it is true that God the Father in the Old Testament and Jesus Christ in the New Testament condemn the performance of rituals if they are nothing more than a hypocritical display of supposed piety, China traditionally placed a strong emphasis on ritual, and Chinese Catholics do in fact usually observe a high degree reverence and piety when praying at Mass or other group or private prayer. One who observes Chinese Catholics at these prayers will often be struck by the degree of fervent participation, singing, chanting, etc., which contrasts with the often more subdued atmosphere in Catholic churches in the west.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Christians are explicitly commanded by Jesus Christ in the gospels to "go and make disciples of all nations" and baptize them in the name of the Father, Son, and Holy Spirit. Chinese Catholics in the PRC period have not gone out to evangelize in this way with as much zeal as Protestant Christians, largely because Catholics have been in a defensive state from a hostile government and Communist party. Since 1949, numbers of Christians both Protestant and Catholic have grown enormously, but Protestant Christianity has grown much more rapidly, and has many more adherents today. This was not the case in the years before 1949.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Stealing is forbidden in the Ten Commandments. Usury, withholding wages, and other forms of economic cheating are also condemned in the Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: It is not quite accurate to say that in Christianity God does not care about personal hygiene--after all, the ritual by which one becomes a Christian, baptism, is a ritual cleansing of the body. Jesus Christ teaches and shows in the gospels, however, that what is important is to be clean in one's heart more than one's body. He demonstrated this by healing and embracing

lepers, considered the most unclean in society, and by telling parables, such as Lazarus and the rich man, in which a poor beggar ends up in heaven, while a rich man who ignored him ends up in fiery torment.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Christianity (including Catholics and Protestants) emphasizes that the faithful, both individually and corporately, enjoy an intimate, familial relationship, or covenant, with the Holy Trinity: Father, Son, and Holy Spirit. Thus, the Old and New Testaments emphasize that the condition of one's heart in relation to God is of the greatest importance, and ritual observances are meaningless unless they support this living relationship.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– I don't know

Notes: Generally Christianity believes that punishment is reserved to God alone: "Vengeance is mine, says the Lord." There is at least one passage in the Psalms which says that punishment of God's enemies will be carried out by His followers, but this is likely not taught as a point of Catholic doctrine, and may be more of a literary device.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Punishment in the afterlife in Christianity is seen only as the result of a person's own choices to willfully separate himself or herself from God, who is the source of all life and goodness. In the absence of all goodness, such a person would experience separation and suffering, but it would not be arbitrary or random.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Traditionally, Catholic thought has characterized Hell as a place or state of eternal fire and torment.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Notes: In Christianity, eternal life is described as perfect, eternal union with God (Father, Son, and Holy Spirit) and all other inhabitants of Heaven: saints, angels, cherubim, etc., who worship God and enjoy pure fellowship with each other. In the Catholic Church, this state is traditionally called the "Beatific vision." (From Wiki) In Christian theology, the beatific vision (Latin: visio beatifica) is the ultimate direct self-communication of God to the individual person. A person possessing the beatific vision reaches, as a member of redeemed humanity in the communion of saints, perfect salvation in its entirety, i.e. heaven.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: There are passages in the Bible, such as the Psalms, which say that those who follow the Lord will be blessed, sometimes with abundance, blessings upon descendants, good health, long life, peace in one's heart, and other things. There are other stories, especially in the Old Testament, of individuals being granted specific requests for a child, victory in battle, and other blessings. The Catholic Church, including in China, teaches that believers may ask God for these things, and as the Psalm says, "give success to the work of our hands." Catholics do not believe, however, that God promises always to grant these requests. Often they are not fulfilled, and Christ, in fact, promised that his followers would undergo sufferings, but that these would lead to greater virtues and eternal life. The greatest gifts, according to the Bible, are spiritual: wisdom, good judgement, love, and other virtues.

Specific to this answer:

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Alive, identified:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Coming has already passed:

– Yes

Notes: Christians believe that the Messiah of Israel and of all humanity is Jesus Christ, who lived in present-day Israel/Palestine around 4 B.C./B.C.E to around 30 A.D./C.E.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Notes: Catholic Christianity, like other Christian traditions and Judaism, upholds the Ten Commandments found in the Old Testament (Exodus 20) as the basic moral standard for believers, and teaches followers to strive for an even higher goal, that of fulfilling Christ's commandments to love God with all one's heart, soul, mind, and strength, and one's neighbor as oneself (Matthew 22: 37-40), and even one's enemies (Matthew 5:44). Richard Madsen observed, however, that moral standards for rural Catholics in China, while upholding the Ten Commandments and Christ's teaching, also reflected the pervasive folk culture. For example, he writes, that in the view of Chinese Catholic villagers, "A good person is someone who has been good for a Catholic community. In practice, loyalty seems to be the cardinal virtue. People of poor character are those who are consistently disloyal, who consistently use others for their own selfish ends." Further, noting the importance Catholic villagers place on the traditional Confucian virtue of filial piety, Madsen continues, "For all the talk about the Ten Commandments...rural Catholic moral imagination is dominated by the Fourth Commandment--honor thy father and mother--and by the virtue of family loyalty, which makes adherence to that commandment reliable and consistent. Loyalty toward parents is both the core of good character and the core of a right relation to God. As a thirty-year-old Catholic mother says, 'Belief in God is just like having filial piety toward parents. A person cannot forget his parents, should speak with them often, should not be indifferent to them'" (Madsen, *China's Catholics*, 79). This emphasis on loyalty, Madsen found, manifests itself in certain results, which can be seen positively or negatively. Those admired most among Catholics are those who have demonstrated the strongest loyalty to Christ during persecution under the Communist Party (1949-present), and have suffered abuse (physical and especially mental abuse is reported to have been especially severe during the Cultural Revolution) or even literal martyrdom. Given the central place of loyalty, says Madsen, "those who are uncompromisingly loyal to fellow Catholics who have loyally suffered martyrdom can claim a preeminent moral superiority." (83) This emphasis on uncompromising loyalty, on the other hand, can also lead to a "rigid intransigence" and factionalism that prevents one from compromise, even when that might be called for by Christ's commands to avoid judging others and to love one's enemies (83). At the same time, Madsen writes

that although those who failed to show a high degree of loyalty and self-sacrifice under persecution, as for example during the Cultural Revolution (1966-1976), are not held up as moral exemplars, they are nevertheless not judged harshly by fellow Catholics (82). Ultimately, Madsen explains, one's conduct is a matter of salvation or damnation (86). See explanations in questions about rewards and punishments.

Reference: Madsen, Richard. *China's Catholics*. University of California Press, 1998.
https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=U_8oMo2hnGMC.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: As explained above, the moral norms revealed by God clearly belong in the moral category, but may overlap with the conventional. As Richard Madsen found, the emphasis on loyalty among Chinese Catholic villagers may constitute an example of a conventional norm being given moral significance by believers. In Madsen's view, the virtue of loyalty in China is sometimes taken to an extreme, and becomes a kind of inflexibility, inability to compromise, or factionalism which becomes harmful to unity or reconciliation in the larger community.

Reference: Madsen, Richard. *China's Catholics*. University of California Press, 1998.
https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=U_8oMo2hnGMC.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Weakly present

Notes: Generally the distinction is present and clear, as in the case of the Ten Commandments, which are displayed in churches, but as Madsen shows, the conventional social values can sometimes be imposed by members of the community on each other as if they were moral values.

Reference: Madsen, Richard. *China's Catholics*. University of California Press, 1998.
https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=U_8oMo2hnGMC.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: See notes on "general social norms" above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

Notes: Moral norms are explicitly linked to God's design for human flourishing. Every positive command leads to human happiness, even if humans find them difficult to keep. Every negative command prohibits something that leads to human unhappiness, and in the church's view this is evident as it plays out in human history.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: This is true if one regards God as an anthropomorphic being. If not, then no.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: This is true if one regards God as an anthropomorphic being. If not, then no. In Christianity, God has made His commands clear, as explained above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

Notes: Moral norms have consequences, both in this life and potentially in eternity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

- ↳ Moral norms apply to:
- All individuals within society
 - All individuals within contemporary world
 - All individuals (any time period)
- Specific to this answer:
Region: Early and early imperial China

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: In the Catholic Church priests in the Latin Rite, which is the largest throughout the world, and includes the Catholic Church in most of the world, including China, are required to take a vow of celibacy and live in a celibate state. Priests in the Eastern Rites (which developed historically in the Middle East and Eastern Europe) are allowed to marry before ordination. Lay persons are allowed to marry and raise families, and sexual activity is allowed and encouraged within marriage. Marriage is between a man and woman who are of age and freely give consent.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: In accord with Catholic teaching on the purpose of sexuality and the flourishing (or

greatest happiness) of human persons, sexual activity is reserved for marriage between a husband and wife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: In accord with Catholic teaching on the purpose of sexuality and the flourishing (or greatest happiness) of human persons, sexual activity is reserved for marriage between a husband and wife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Members are instructed to observe fasting or abstinence from meat on certain Holy Days, primarily during the season of Lent, 40 days preceding Easter. Many Catholics in China also choose to observe an older Catholic practice and abstain from meat on Fridays throughout the entire year.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: The Catholic Church teaches that the faithful have an obligation to participate in the Mass on Sundays. In practice, many Catholics participate less often than this, and there is no punishment imposed by the Church, although the Church regards willful neglect of the Sunday obligation as a sin against God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: In China, members of the unregistered or underground church often gather in private locations, and gatherings may average from a few persons to several hundred. Given the difficulties under which they live, it is probably not accurate to say that participation in such private gatherings is required, although many underground Catholics faithfully attend regularly if possible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Reference: Clark, Anthony E.. “China's Thriving Catholics: A Report from Beijing's South Cathedral”.
Ignatius Insight, August 20, 2008.

http://www.ignatiusinsight.com/features2008/aclark_china1_aug08.asp.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no "average" for this. Numbers vary from a few individuals to millions of faithful. Some of the largest gatherings in human history, numbering in the millions, have been Catholic masses. In China, in cities the largest numbers range in the hundreds to a few thousand. The government tries to prevent extremely large gatherings. In rural areas, believers may gather in small groups of 2 to 10 persons for prayer or underground (illegal) masses. For photos of underground Catholics, see photographs by Lu Nan, listed in the Bibliography.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 168

Notes: Masses are typically offered every Sunday. On Sundays, a given Catholic church may offer only one mass, if it is in a small village, or several large masses if in a city. The interval may be anywhere from a few minutes (or none) to several hours between masses. In very remote locations, masses may be available less frequently than once a week, or may even only be offered once a month or once a year.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Priests are trained and expected to follow liturgical texts prescribed for the whole country and the church worldwide. Chinese Catholics value this connection to the worldwide church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Same as previous answer.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: If the following is what is meant by "fictive kinship terminology": Catholic priests are addressed as "Father [+ name]," vowed religious women as "Sister" or "Mother" [+ name] and vowed religious men who are not priests as "Brother [+ name]. If this is what is meant by "fictive kinship terminology," then yes. In China, the terms of address, while equivalent, are not the same. A priest in China is addressed as "[Surname (e.g. Ren)] + Shenfu 神父 ("Holy father"), while sisters and nuns are addressed as "[name] = Xiūnǚ 修女, or literally, "excellent woman" or "cultivated woman." Xiūnǚ doesn't mean "sister," and the male equivalent "Xiushi" 修士 doesn't mean "brother" as it does in western languages, but literally "cultivated bachelor."

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: A Catholic priest or sister from anywhere in the world is called "Father" or "Sister" by Catholics anywhere else in the world.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Notes: The above noted is common practice among Catholics (and many non-Catholics also refer

to priests as "Father" and sisters as "Sister."

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: In the Catholic Church priests in the Latin Rite, which is the largest throughout the world, and includes the Catholic Church in most of the world, including China, are required to take a vow of celibacy and live in a celibate state. Priests in the Eastern Rites (which developed historically in the Middle East and Eastern Europe) are allowed to marry before ordination. Lay persons are allowed to marry and raise families, and sexual activity is allowed and encouraged within marriage. Marriage is between a man and woman who are of age and freely give consent.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: In accord with Catholic teaching on the purpose of sexuality and the flourishing (or greatest happiness) of human persons, sexual activity is reserved for marriage between a husband and wife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: In accord with Catholic teaching on the purpose of sexuality and the flourishing (or greatest happiness) of human persons, sexual activity is reserved for marriage between a husband and wife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Members are instructed to observe fasting or abstinence from meat on certain Holy Days, primarily during the season of Lent, 40 days preceding Easter. Many Catholics in China also choose to observe an older Catholic practice and abstain from meat on Fridays throughout the entire year.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: The Catholic Church teaches that the faithful have an obligation to participate in the Mass on Sundays. In practice, many Catholics participate less often than this, and there is no punishment imposed by the Church, although the Church regards willful neglect of the Sunday obligation as a sin against God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: In China, members of the unregistered or underground church often gather in private locations, and gatherings may average from a few persons to several hundred. Given the difficulties under which they live, it is probably not accurate to say that participation in such private gatherings is required, although many underground Catholics faithfully attend regularly if possible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Reference: Clark, Anthony E.. “China's Thriving Catholics: A Report from Beijing's South Cathedral”. Ignatius Insight, August 20, 2008.

http://www.ignatiusinsight.com/features2008/aclark_china1_aug08.asp.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no “average” for this. Numbers vary from a few individuals to millions of faithful. Some of the largest gatherings in human history, numbering in the millions, have been Catholic masses. In China, in cities the largest numbers range in the hundreds to a few thousand. The government tries to prevent extremely large gatherings. In rural areas, believers may gather in small groups of 2 to 10 persons for prayer or underground (illegal) masses. For photos of underground Catholics, see photographs by Lu Nan, listed in the Bibliography.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 168

Notes: Masses are typically offered every Sunday. On Sundays, a given Catholic church may offer only one mass, if it is in a small village, or several large masses if in a city. The interval may be anywhere from a few minutes (or none) to several hours between masses. In very remote locations, masses may be available less frequently than once a week, or may even only be offered once a month or once a year.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Priests are trained and expected to follow liturgical texts prescribed for the whole country and the church worldwide. Chinese Catholics value this connection to the worldwide church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Same as previous answer.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: If the following is what is meant by "fictive kinship terminology": Catholic priests are addressed as "Father [+ name]," vowed religious women as "Sister" or "Mother" [+ name] and vowed religious men who are not priests as "Brother [+ name]. If this is what is meant by "fictive kinship terminology," then yes. In China, the terms of address, while equivalent, are not the same. A priest in China is addressed as "[Surname (e.g. Ren)] + Shenfu 神父 ("Holy father"), while sisters and nuns are addressed as "[name] = Xiūnǚ 修女, or literally, "excellent woman" or "cultivated woman." Xiūnǚ doesn't mean "sister," and the male equivalent "Xiushi" 修士 doesn't mean "brother" as it does in western languages, but literally "cultivated bachelor."

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: A Catholic priest or sister from anywhere in the world is called "Father" or "Sister" by Catholics anywhere else in the world.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Notes: The above noted is common practice among Catholics (and many non-Catholics also refer to priests as "Father" and sisters as "Sister."

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: *Formal education by religious groups is strictly controlled by the government, and at present it is forbidden to provide religious instruction to youth under age 18. The Catholic church in China is not allowed to run its own schools as it does in many other countries. By law at least, educational programs offered in churches must be approved in advance by government authorities. Seminaries train students for priesthood and religious life, but are also controlled by the state. The unregistered (underground) church has historically carried out religious education despite these prohibitions, but this has become more dangerous during tightened state control over religions in recent years under the rule of Communist Party General Secretary Xi Jinping. It is possible that Catholics in remote areas still provide formal education, especially for primary school children.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: The Pope has a group of protectors called the Pontifical Swiss Guard, who are known by their renaissance uniforms and serve only in Vatican City. They serve as bodyguards and palace guards and have military training.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

Notes: The Swiss Guard.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: Many Chinese Catholics live in rural areas, so those who are farmers would provide food for themselves. In urban areas this is not the case.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The Church's liturgical year is marked by a calendar that defines liturgical seasons (i.e., lent, Easter, Advent, Christmas, Ordinary Time), and marks feast days of Saints and other Holy Days.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Most Chinese Catholics obtain food as to others in their particular rural or urban location, through markets.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Government taxes applied to all citizens.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Catholics in China attend state schools and universities like other Chinese citizens. In the past, being known to officials as a Christian (Catholic or Protestant) has reportedly created barriers to or limits on one's educational opportunities, and therefore some students have likely tried to hide their religious affiliation in order to attend schools of their choice. It is reported that this situation of discrimination based on one's religion may be rising again.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but as explained above, education is managed by the state, and theoretically open to Catholics as to other citizens. Non-religious private schools also exist, but any religiously affiliated private schools are open only to foreign nationals living in China.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Government police and security forces. Since the 1950s, when the government, led by the Chinese Communist Party, began a campaign to control religious groups, and to persecute groups that refused to join government-approved "patriotic associations," Catholics, especially in the underground church, have suffered persecution, as have adherents of other religions. During crackdowns, religious leaders and sometimes lay believers have been targeted and at times harassed, detained, jailed, or executed. A detailed account of such a campaign during the 1950s is given in the book *Church Militant: Bishop Kung and Catholic Resistance in Communist Shanghai* by Paul P. Mariani. News websites including AsiaNews.it and UCANews.com report on current cases of persecution against Catholics and other religious believers in China.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Along with all citizens, Catholics in China learn written Chinese in state schools.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: The registered Catholic Church in at least some dioceses has its own charitable organizations, such as, for example, Jinde Charities in Hebei province. These provide some limited poverty relief (in various forms, such as care for the elderly, medical care in under-served areas, scholarship aid, and special grants for medical procedures) for local Catholics and non-Catholics. They also engage in disaster-relief efforts after events such as floods and earthquakes. These organizations work with international Catholic charities in carrying out poverty-relief efforts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As above, most Chinese Catholics learn to write Chinese through state schools.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Provided by government.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Government institutions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: At least some Catholic charities provide institutionalized care for the elderly.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: The church does not impose punishments on its members. In some instances the Church imposes ecclesial discipline. For example, if a Catholic theologian publishes views that oppose fundamental Church teachings the Church may, after investigation, forbid that person to publish as a Catholic theologian, or to teach in a Catholic theology department. Bishops or priests whose teaching conflicts with church teaching or whose conduct causes serious scandal may be removed from ministry or laicized, that is, removed from the priesthood. Catholic laypersons or clergy may incur an automatic (or public) excommunication for certain grave offenses, such as apostasy (the rejection of Christian faith), heresy (the obstinate denial of a truth of the faith), or schism (the rejection of the pope's authority as head of the Church). In most cases the Church does not apply these in a systematic manner, but on occasion does publicly announce the excommunications if deemed appropriate, as in the case of certain historical figures. In China, the church did excommunicate seven bishops in the official church who had been ordained without the required mandate from the pope. In 2018, as part of the Sino-Vatican agreement, all seven of these excommunications were lifted, and these bishops were approved by the Holy See. This move was opposed by some, especially in the underground church, who viewed it as rewarding bishops who previously committed an act of serious disobedience.

<http://www.asianews.it/news-en/The-excommunication-of-seven-illegitimate-bishops-lifted,-the-new-Diocese-of-Chengde-established-for-Mgr-Guo-Jincai-45012.html>

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Catholics are subject to the same national laws and punishments as other citizens. In addition, while the PRC's constitution guarantees "freedom of religious belief" and the protection of "normal" religious activities, without specifying what activities are regarded as "normal," according to human rights and governmental groups that monitor religious freedom, PRC authorities in practice violate the religious freedom of Catholics in ways that violate international human rights norms, such as the Universal Declaration on Human Rights (UDHR) and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR). From the 1950s until the present, with varying degrees of intensity during different political eras, Catholics, like believers of many other religions, have been subjected to excessive controls

and coercion that violate their rights to religious freedom.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: Like any other citizen, a Catholic may be executed if convicted of a crime carrying this punishment.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

– Yes

Notes: As noted above, Catholics who suffer persecution may be subjected to beatings, torture, or other corporal punishments, as may members of other religious groups or any citizen suspected of crimes against the state. In recent years, reports of Catholics suffering these kinds of corporal punishments have been relatively few, compared with members of religious groups deemed "illegal" or xiejiao ("cults") such as Falun Gong, Church of Almighty God, or others. There have been several underground Catholic clergy, however, who have been detained and possibly tortured in recent years. In particular, two underground Catholic bishops, James Su Zhimin and Cosmas Shi Enxiang, who were disappeared in 1997 and 2001, respectively, have not been heard from since their detentions. There have been unconfirmed reports that Bishop Shi died in state custody in or before 2015, and some have suspected that Bishop Su may have died in or before 2020, based on official moves to replace him.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

— Yes

Notes: From the 1950s until the late 1970s (including the period of repression called the Cultural Revolution, 1966-76), government authorities seized church properties throughout China, and in many cases demolished churches, or expelled believers and used the properties for secular purposes, such as army barracks, storage facilities, or to house livestock. Beginning in the late 1970s, religious activities were legally allowed to resume, and many properties were returned to the church, although some, such as formerly Catholic schools were not.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: Provided by government.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

— Yes

Notes: (from Wikipedia) The canon law of the Catholic Church (Latin: *ius canonicum*) is the system of laws and legal principles made and enforced by the hierarchical authorities of the Catholic Church to regulate its external organization and government and to order and direct the activities of Catholics toward the mission of the Church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: Catholics in China are subject to national laws, as described above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: The registered Catholic Church in at least some dioceses has its own charitable organizations, such as, for example, Jinde Charities in Hebei province. These provide some limited poverty relief (in various forms, such as care for the elderly, medical care in under-served areas, scholarship aid, and special grants for medical procedures) for local Catholics and non-Catholics. They also engage in disaster-relief efforts after events such as floods and earthquakes. These organizations work with international Catholic charities in carrying out poverty-relief efforts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: At least some Catholic charities provide institutionalized care for the elderly.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: *Formal education by religious groups is strictly controlled by the government, and at present it is forbidden to provide religious instruction to youth under age 18. The Catholic church in China is not allowed to run its own schools as it does in many other countries. By law at least, educational programs offered in churches must be approved in advance by government authorities. Seminaries train students for priesthood and religious life, but are also controlled by the state. The unregistered (underground) church has historically carried out religious education despite these prohibitions, but this has become more dangerous during tightened state control over religions in recent years under the rule of Communist Party General Secretary Xi Jinping. It is possible that Catholics in remote areas still provide formal education, especially for primary school children.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Catholics in China attend state schools and universities like other Chinese citizens. In the past, being known to officials as a Christian (Catholic or Protestant) has reportedly created barriers to or limits on one's educational opportunities, and therefore some students have likely tried to hide their religious affiliation in order to attend schools of their choice. It is reported that this situation of discrimination based on one's religion may be rising again.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but as explained above, education is managed by the state, and theoretically open to Catholics as to other citizens. Non-religious private schools also exist, but any religiously affiliated private schools are open only to foreign nationals living in China.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Provided by government.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Provided by government.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Government taxes applied to all citizens.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Government police and security forces. Since the 1950s, when the government, led by the Chinese Communist Party, began a campaign to control religious groups, and to persecute groups that refused to join government-approved "patriotic associations," Catholics, especially in the underground church, have suffered persecution, as have adherents of other religions. During crackdowns, religious leaders and sometimes lay believers have been targeted and at times harassed, detained, jailed, or executed. A detailed account of such a campaign during the 1950s is given in the book *Church Militant: Bishop Kung and Catholic Resistance in Communist Shanghai* by Paul P. Mariani. News websites including AsiaNews.it and UCANews.com report on current cases of persecution against Catholics and other religious believers in China.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Government institutions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: The church does not impose punishments on its members. In some instances the Church imposes ecclesial discipline. For example, if a Catholic theologian publishes views that oppose fundamental Church teachings the Church may, after investigation, forbid that person to publish as a Catholic theologian, or to teach in a Catholic theology department. Bishops or priests whose teaching conflicts with church teaching or whose conduct causes serious scandal may be removed from ministry or laicized, that is, removed from the priesthood. Catholic laypersons or clergy may incur an automatic (or public) excommunication for certain grave offenses, such as apostasy (the rejection of Christian faith), heresy (the obstinate denial of a truth of the faith), or schism (the rejection of the pope's authority as head of the Church). In most cases the Church does not apply these in a systematic manner, but on occasion does publicly announce the excommunications if deemed appropriate, as in the case of certain historical figures. In China, the church did excommunicate seven bishops in the official church who had been ordained without the required mandate from the pope. In 2018, as part of the Sino-Vatican agreement, all seven of these excommunications were lifted, and these bishops were approved by the Holy See. This move was opposed by some, especially in the underground church, who viewed it as rewarding bishops who previously committed an act of serious disobedience. <http://www.asianews.it/news-en/The-excommunication-of-seven-illegitimate-bishops-lifted,-the-new-Diocese-of-Chengde-established-for-Mgr-Guo-Jincai-45012.html>

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Catholics are subject to the same national laws and punishments as other citizens. In addition, while the PRC's constitution guarantees "freedom of religious belief" and the protection of "normal" religious activities, without specifying what activities are regarded as "normal," according to human rights and governmental groups that monitor religious freedom, PRC authorities in practice violate the religious freedom of Catholics in ways that violate international human rights norms, such as the Universal Declaration on Human Rights (UDHR) and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR). From the 1950s until the present, with varying degrees of intensity during different political eras, Catholics, like believers of many other religions, have been subjected to excessive controls and coercion that violate their rights to religious freedom.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: Like any other citizen, a Catholic may be executed if convicted of a crime carrying this punishment.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

– Yes

Notes: As noted above, Catholics who suffer persecution may be subjected to beatings, torture, or other corporal punishments, as may members of other religious groups or any citizen suspected of crimes against the state. In recent years, reports of Catholics suffering these kinds of corporal punishments have been relatively few, compared with members of religious groups deemed "illegal" or xiejiao ("cults") such as Falun Gong, Church of Almighty God, or others. There have been several underground Catholic clergy, however, who have been detained and possibly tortured in recent years. In particular, two underground Catholic bishops, James Su

Zhimin and Cosmas Shi Enxiang, who were disappeared in 1997 and 2001, respectively, have not been heard from since their detentions. There have been unconfirmed reports that Bishop Shi died in state custody in or before 2015, and some have suspected that Bishop Su may have died in or before 2020, based on official moves to replace him.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: From the 1950s until the late 1970s (including the period of repression called the Cultural Revolution, 1966-76), government authorities seized church properties throughout China, and in many cases demolished churches, or expelled believers and used the properties for secular purposes, such as army barracks, storage facilities, or to house livestock. Beginning in the late 1970s, religious activities were legally allowed to resume, and many properties were returned to the church, although some, such as formerly Catholic schools were not.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: (from Wikipedia) The canon law of the Catholic Church (Latin: *ius canonicum*) is the system of laws and legal principles made and enforced by the hierarchical authorities of the Catholic Church to regulate its external organization and government and to order and direct the activities of Catholics toward the mission of the Church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Catholics in China are subject to national laws, as described above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: The Pope has a group of protectors called the Pontifical Swiss Guard, who are known by their renaissance uniforms and serve only in Vatican City. They serve as bodyguards and palace guards and have military training.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

Notes: The Swiss Guard.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Along with all citizens, Catholics in China learn written Chinese in state schools.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As above, most Chinese Catholics learn to write Chinese through state schools.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The Church's liturgical year is marked by a calendar that defines liturgical seasons (i.e., lent, Easter, Advent, Christmas, Ordinary Time), and marks feast days of Saints and other Holy Days.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: Many Chinese Catholics live in rural areas, so those who are farmers would provide food for themselves. In urban areas this is not the case.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Most Chinese Catholics obtain food as to others in their particular rural or urban location, through markets.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Early and early imperial China

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